

Phthalazines(III) are colourless crystalline solids, sparingly soluble in organic solvents, soluble in dilute alkali, insoluble in dilute mineral acids and are characterised by high melting points. They give cherry red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

1,4-Dihydroxyphthalazines (IV) :

A mixture of phthalimide (0.03M) and 99% hydrazine hydrate (0.032M) was heated on a sand bath with PPA at 220° for 30 minutes and allowed to cool. The mass was decomposed with ice water and crystallised from acetic acid-ethanol (1 : 2) mixture. 6-Benzoylamino-1, 4-dihydroxyphthalazine is newly prepared (m. p. 329°d ; yield 86%).

1, 4-Dihydroxyphthalazines are characterised by high melting points with decomposition, they give reddish-brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Further work along this line is in progress.

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Synthesis of New 5-(2-Oxo-3-Indolinylidene)-3-Benzyl-2-Arylimino-4-Thiazolidinones Derived from 3-Benzyl-2-Arylimino-4-Thiazolidinones

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CONDENSATIONS of 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones with isatin has been reported to yield thioindigoid dyes^{1,2}. Using this approach, new

seventeen 5-(2-oxo-3-indolinylidene)-3-benzyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones (3) (Table 1) have been prepared by condensing isatin (1) with 3-benzyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones (2) in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and glacial acetic acid. Various 3-benzyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones were obtained from 1-benzyl-3-aryl-2-thioureas and monochloroacetic acid³. These dyes were coloured from deep-orange to dark-red and dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid producing dark coloured solution.

TABLE 1—5-(2-Oxo-3-INDOLINYLIIDENE)-3-BENZYL-2-ARYLIMINO 4-THIAZOLIDINONES (3)

S. No.	Ar.	Yield	m.p. °C	Colour
1.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	77	190	dark-red
2.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	77	205	dark-red
3.	<i>o</i> -Phenetyl	86	212	orange-red
4.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	79	205	orange-red
5.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	70	200	dark-red
6.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	71	116	dark-red
7.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	80	95	dark-red
8.	<i>o</i> -Bromophenyl	81	150	dark-red
9.	<i>p</i> Bromophenyl	81	125	dark-red
10.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	91	180	Red
11.	2,5-Dichlorophenyl	73	(decompn.) 135	dark-red
12.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	77	(decompn.) 70 (melts with charring)	blackish- red
13.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	84	75 (decompn.)	red
14.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	77	170 (decompn.)	blackish- red
15.	4-Hydroxy-2-methylphenyl	71	175	dark-red
16.	1-Naphthyl	72	volatile at 260°	red
17.	2-Pyridyl	76	280	bright-red

Experimental

All melting points have been taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

The following general procedure as exemplified for the synthesis of 5-(2-oxo-3-indolinylidene)-3-benzyl-2-(1-naphthylimino)-4-thiazolidinone was adopted for the preparation of all the thioindigoid dyes.

A mixture of 3-benzyl-2-(1-naphthylimino)-4-thiazolidinone (3.32g, 0.01 mole), isatin (1.5g, 0.01 mole), anhydrous sodium acetate (3.2g, 0.04 mole), glacial acetic acid (40 ml) and acetic anhydride (4ml) were refluxed for about 4.5 hrs. After cooling the reaction mixture was poured into cold water when a red precipitate was formed. The precipitate was filtered, washed successively with hot water, dilute acetic acid and finally several times with ethanol and dried.

The IR spectrum (nujol) showed characteristic peaks at 3200 cm^{-1} (NH); $2950, 2880\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (CH_2); $1740, 1720\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); 1650 cm^{-1} (aliphatic $\text{C}=\text{C}$); 1615 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$); $1596, 1480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (aromatic $\text{C}=\text{C}$) and 740 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{S}$).

All of them showed consistent elemental analysis.

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A New Synthesis of Murrayacinine

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In a previous communication, we reported the structure and synthesis of murrayacinine (I), a carbazole alkaloid isolated from the stem-bark of *Murraya koenigii* Spreng. The synthesis involved condensation of citral with 2-hydroxy-3-formyl carbazole (II) which in turn was obtained by chromic acid oxidation of 2-hydroxy-3-methyl carbazole (III). In consideration of the relatively poor yield of the alkaloid obtained in our previous synthesis and in view of the fact that murrayacinine (I) is an oxidative variant of the alkaloid mahanimbine (IV)², a facile conversion

of IV to I was achieved by the use of DDQ (dichloro-dicyano benzoquinone), a reagent that has recently been used³⁻⁵ for similar oxidation of aromatic methyl groups to corresponding formyl groups. Mahanimbine in dry benzene was stirred with DDQ at room temperature for 2 hours. The product was then taken in ether, washed with 1% NaOH and water. From the reaction mixture murrayacinine was isolated by preparative thin layer method.

- (I) $\text{R}_1 = -\text{CHO}$; $\text{R}_2 = \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}=\text{C} \begin{matrix} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{matrix}$
- (II) $\text{R}_1 = -\text{CHO}$; $\text{R}_2 = -\text{OH}$
- (III) $\text{R}_1 = -\text{CH}_3$; $\text{R}_2 = -\text{OH}$
- (IV) $\text{R}_1 = -\text{CH}_3$; $\text{R}_2 = \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}=\text{C} \begin{matrix} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{matrix}$

Experimental

Mahanimbine (50 mg) in dry benzene (10 ml) was stirred and a solution of DDQ in dry benzene (molar proportion) was added to it over a period of 15 minutes. The stirring was continued for 1 hour at room temperature. The reaction product was then treated with 1% NaOH and extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed with water to free it from alkali and dried over sodium sulphate.

After the removal of the ether the residue was taken in benzene and subjected to preparative t. l. c. The spot identical with natural murrayacinine was scraped out from the t.l.c. plate, extracted with alcohol and filtered. The solid obtained on evaporation of the alcohol was purified and recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture. The compound was finally identified as murrayacinine (yield 15 mg) by a direct comparison with a pure specimen of the sample (uv, ir, m.p., m.m.p., t.l.c.). The other constituents in the chromatogram was not characterised due to poor yield.

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